

SIMMAM 3.0 – Updating the Toolbox for the Conservation of Marine Mammals

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Abstract

The conservation of species depends on the availability of distribution data over time. Without knowledge of where a species occur, management actions are seriously hindered and cannot evaluate if actions are successful or not. SIMMAM (Sistema de Apoio ao Monitoramento de Mamíferos Marinhos) was developed to aggregate occurrence data for marine mammals and serve as a platform where for researchers and environmental agencies can deposit and visualize occurrence data in Brazil and has been available since 2005. During its lifetime, it was updated, to adapt to new standards and data sharing policies. SIMMAM 3.0 uses modern technologies (PHP 7.4, Symfony 5.x, PostgreSQL 11.x, PostGIS 3.x, Leaflet 1.7) and is compliant to DarwinCore (DwC) standard and able to exchange data with other data portals that use it. Its database now holds more than 68000 marine mammal records and is an important tool in the decision-making process of Brazilian environmental agencies.

1.0 Introduction

Marine mammals are often found in low densities and difficult to access areas, being a group that is comparatively less known than terrestrial mammals. However, they are under diverse threats from human activities, which include direct and accidental capture, loss of habitat due to pollution and degradation, underwater noise and many others (Avila et al., 2018; Nicol et al., 2020; Secchi et al., 2023). The lack of data on their distribution hinders conservation efforts, as without knowledge of previous occurrence it is not possible to evaluate if they are becoming scarce or not.

Stranded marine mammals serve as valuable sources of information, providing biological samples that contribute to our understanding of their occurrence and biological parameters. Sightings of live animals at sea can inform on their distribution and allow inferences of what parameters are relevant for their distribution (Cañadas et al., 2018; Pasanisi et al., 2024). However, since strandings are infrequent and sightings in oceanic areas are expensive to acquire, it is crucial to accumulate data from broad geographic areas and over extended periods for the information to be biologically meaningful. Various global initiatives have highlighted the importance of digital databases for studying and conserving species, such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF; Edwards et al., 2000) and the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS; Halpin et al., 2009).

In Brazil marine mammals have been systematically studied by research groups since the 1970s (e.g. Castello and Pinedo, 1977a, b), initially describing the existing species and afterwards focusing on their ecology and interaction with human activities. Research groups maintained their own records, organizing them according to specific research objectives. With the accumulation of data and the development of the internet, it became clear that to have a better understanding of the problems faced by marine mammals in Brazil it was necessary to integrate these disparate datasets.

The SIMMAM (Sistema de Apoio ao Monitoramento de Mamíferos Marinhos) project started in early 2000s to organize a database of marine mammal sightings and strandings along the Brazilian coast. It began as an internal project at the Universidade do Vale do Itajaí - UNIVALI (Itajaí Valley

University) to organize data from projects coordinated by UNIVALI researchers. The initial modelling of the system was developed by a partnership between the Laboratório de Oceanografia Biológica (Biological Oceanography Laboratory) and the Laboratório de Computação Aplicada (Applied Computing Laboratory, presently Laboratório de Informática da Biodiversidade e Geomática – LIBGeo). The SIMMAM system is available at <https://libgeo.univali.br/simmam>.

The system had its initial implementation as part of a Masterthesis (Moraes, 2005), that aimed at structuring a GIS with data on sightings, strandings and accidental captures of cetaceans. From its onset SIMMAM was thought as a tool that would facilitate the study of distribution and occupation patterns of cetaceans on the Brazilian coast. Initially, occurrence data came from historical data published in the scientific literature and sighting data collected by scientific observers on fishing vessels that participated in UNIVALI's projects.

After the system was implemented and fed with this initial data, it was presented to Brazilian environmental agencies during technical meetings. At that time the Centro Mamíferos Aquáticos – CMA, formerly a part of IBAMA and now of ICMBio, was coordinating the implementation of the Brazilian stranding network and was already integrating data from different institutions. However, this was done by filling spreadsheets and exchanging them by e-mail. CMA noticed that SIMMAM could accelerate this data integration and reduce errors in the process. Thus, an agreement for technical cooperation was signed between UNIVALI and CMA, to further develop SIMMAM and jointly manage it.

As part of this agreement an effort was directed to review sighting data from reports held by IBAMA originating from marine mammal observers (MMOs) onboard seismic survey ships. Up to that moment, sighting reports were received by IBAMA and after conference were stored either physically on paper or digitally in CD-ROMs. Review of these reports resulted in approximately 7,400 sighting records that were standardized and inserted in SIMMAM (Britto, 2009).

Its initial implementation has already been described (Moraes, 2005; Barreto et al., 2006) and was based on PHP 5.0 and Adobe Flex 3.0. Considering the development of new technologies and communication protocols, SIMMAM had to evolve to adapt to

this new environment. This paper describes its new implementation and the evolution of its database in terms of contributions from different parties.

2.0 Technologies

Technology has advanced rapidly in recent decades, impacting computational tools, communication protocols, data-sharing policies, and availability. To meet the needs of researchers and Brazilian environmental agencies, SIMMAM was extensively modernized using current technologies. Changes included internal updates and the implementation of a communication protocol to ensure compatibility with existing data aggregators.

SIMMAM 3.0 now conforms to the DarwinCore (DwC) standard, an international scientific initiative of the Taxonomic Database Working Group (TDWG). The data architecture adopted is compatible with GBIF, allowing SIMMAM to become a data publisher of marine mammal occurrences.

In developing SIMMAM 3.0, we decided to maintain the premise of using free source code tools. The system's development followed the MVC methodology. On the server side, PHP 7.4 was used with the Symfony 5.x framework. For the web client side, we opted to render the site on the server side and deliver an HTML + JavaScript page with Bootstrap 5 to the browser (Figure 1). The data exchange API was also implemented in PHP, following DwC's XML standard.

Figure 1. Simplified block diagram for SIMMAM 3.0.

Data is stored in PostgreSQL 11.x with PostGIS 3.x which allows manipulation of geospatialized data. The tables were structured according to the DwC standard (Figure 2), to reduce the complexity of the communication API.

Stranding, sighting, and accidental capture records have a hierarchy in terms of storage in the database. These tables have a common inheritance, which is the record table. This table is responsible for persisting the basic and shared data between the three types of records, such as event date, latitude and longitude, and status.

Priority was given to using controlled vocabulary for the values entered. Where possible, this was done to facilitate the management of values for fields with controlled vocabularies, such as species, weather, and sea state. This controlled vocabulary is managed through auxiliary tables that store lists of allowed values for each field. When inserting a new record, the system validates the values entered to ensure they comply with the predefined lists.

To ensure the security of private data, a business rule was implemented that compartmentalizes all data, preventing other users from seeing it. The only exception is for users in the 'Environmental Agency' category, who can see all the data, as

they need access to all occurrences for decision-making purposes.

Figure 2 Relationship diagram for the main entities in SIMMAM 3.0.

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A crucial aspect of biological information is taxonomic identification. With advancements in the field, organisms previously identified at a taxon (e.g., family, genus, species) may undergo name changes. To avoid taxonomic instability, SIMMAM uses the taxonomic list provided by the Integrated Taxonomic Information System – ITIS (www.itis.gov). It aims to provide reliable information on species names and their hierarchical classification, with curatorship of the species listings to keep them up to date. As the taxonomic classification of mammals is relatively stable, it was decided to keep a copy of the ITIS database locally to reduce latency, being updated on demand. In order to guarantee that the identification is as accurate as possible, users are instructed to report only the taxonomic level that they have certainty. Thus, only the genus must be recorded if there is a doubt about the species.

The types of occurrence records currently supported by SIMMAM are strandings, accidental captures, and sightings. All these occurrence records have fields for defining the best taxonomic level, georeferencing the occurrence, information on biological material collected, and the user responsible for the data. Stranding and accidental capture records contain information regarding the state of the animal (alive or dead), the condition of the carcass (decomposition stage), sex, and length. For sightings, it is possible to inform environmental parameters such as weather conditions, sea state, and wind speed. Information regarding the animals can also be inserted, including if it was a single animal, part of a group, and group size. As quantifying groups of cetaceans at sea is notoriously difficult, instead of using a single value for the number of animals, as used in strandings, the group size uses three values: minimum, best estimate, and maximum. If the user is confident about the number of sighted animals, they must repeat the same value in all three fields.

While some variables are optional depending on the record type, the geographic position is mandatory in all three categories. As all occurrences in SIMMAM need a geographic position, the primary interface for users to view the data is through an interactive WebGIS. The WebGIS implemented filters by taxon and type of occurrence (sighting, stranding, incidental capture)

to allow users to focus on specific groups of organisms or kinds of data.

A performance evaluation was carried out between the Leaflet 1.6.0 (Agafonkin, 2020) and OpenLayers 5.3.x libraries to build the SIMMAM interactive map. The tests used GeoJSON files with approximately 80,000 features in different browsers (Firefox, Chrome, and Edge). The results showed that Leaflet 1.6.0 performed better, with a 40% shorter initial loading time and a more stable frame rate during interaction, even with large volumes of data. Considering the project's requirements, which included loading time, fluidity when navigating, and number of points, Leaflet 1.6.0 was chosen as the most suitable library to guarantee a fluid and intuitive user experience.

A dynamic clustering method was implemented to better display areas with a high density of records, automatically grouping and ungrouping records according to the zoom level (Figure 3). This dynamic clustering allows the user to view hotspots of occurrences without generating visual clutter. In the webGIS construction, Leaflet Map (Agafonkin, 2020) was used with the OpenStreetMap base map, as it is a modern map engine with functionalities optimized for mobile devices and no external dependencies. Leaflet supports multiple layers and is compatible with the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards, such as support for map mosaics, georeferenced images, WMS (Leaflet, 2020), and GeoJSON (IETF, 2021).

However, as users might need to manipulate data differently, exporting data in spreadsheets (XLS format) is possible. For public records, the exported spreadsheet has all the information the user inserted for each record type, such as species, geographic position, date, group size, and any other information. However, only the taxonomic information and the user responsible for inserting the data are exported for private data. Informing who is the user responsible for that data allows the person interested in using the data to contact the user and discuss if and how the information can be shared. The SIMMAM managers do not interfere with the decision of the users to share or not the data under their responsibilities.

As strandings, accidental captures, and sightings may be visible simultaneously, different geometric shapes (circle, triangle, and square) were chosen to represent the data types. This strategy improves visual distinction, especially for people with color blindness. A circle was used for strandings, a triangle for accidental catches, and a square for sightings. Another important aspect of the data is whether it is public or private; color was used to discriminate this variable. Another effective way of improving visual accessibility was to use high-contrast colors (yellow and A B red) to indicate the status of the record (public or private) (Figure 4).

3.0 Implementation and Use by the Scientific Community

The first version of SIMMAM was made available to the Centro Mamíferos Aquáticos - CMA. In 2007, it started to use SIMMAM as the primary tool to integrate data of the different institutions that composed the Brazilian Stranding Network of Aquatic Mammals (Rede de Encalhes de Mamíferos Aquáticos do Brasil, REMAB). In the same year, SIMMAM was presented to the then General Coordination of Oil and Gas (Coordenação Geral de Petróleo e Gás – CGPEG), current General Coordination of Marine and Coastal Enterprises (Coordenação-Geral de Licenciamento Ambiental de Empreendimentos Marinhos e Costeiros – CGMAC), which identified the

possibility of using it to aggregate and organize marine mammal sighting data generated by marine mammal observers – MMOs (Barreto et al., 2019).

Figure 3 Example of the dynamic clustering implemented in SIMMAM 3.0 WebGIS, showing (A) data aggregated in lowzoom, (B) individual data points in higher zoom.

Figure 4. WebGIS symbology for different types of data. A circle was used for strandings, a triangle for incidental catches and a square for sightings. Colors (yellow and red) to indicate the status of the record (public or non-public).

A cooperation agreement was signed between UNIVALI and IBAMA for the review of MMO reports between 2000 and 2008, organizing and inserting all marine mammal data in SIMMAM (BRITTO; 2009). From 2009 onwards, the obligation to upload sightinging data directly to SIMMAM was transferred to helicensed companies. In 2010, a research grant was awarded to SIMMAM as part of the Brazilian government's SISBIOTA initiative. This grant strengthened the network of scientific institutions that contributed data to SIMMAM, resulting in an increase in the inclusion of data in 2013, with the finalization of this grant (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Temporal evolution of data included in SIMMAM, separated in sightings, strandings and accidental captures.

After the SISBIOTA grant finished in 2013, data input was mainly done by the oil industry, as this was part of the licensing process for seismic surveys. As can be seen in Figure 5, in 2020 and 2023, large numbers of stranding records were inserted in SIMMAM. In both cases this was the result of data that was being collected by beach monitoring projects and kept in separate repositories and were later added to SIMMAM. In 2020 data came from the Projeto de Monitoramento de Praias da Bacia de Santos—PMP-BS that started in 2016, and monitors almost 1500km of beaches (PETROBRAS, 2023). In 2023 data came from other smaller beach monitoring projects from the southeast and northeast Brazilian coast. Together, the addition of this data almost doubled the number of stranding records previously held by SIMMAM.

As of December 2023, SIMMAM had 353 active users and held 67,692 aquatic mammal records. Of these, 44,6% of records are private, but this proportion is very different depending on the type of record (Figure 5). For strandings 57% are private as they are the results of efforts of separate research groups along the Brazilian coast, and until 2016 were the primary source of this data type. However, 72% of sightings are public, as they come primarily from the oil industry as part of the environmental licensing of their operations. Sightinging records from MMOs on board seismic survey vessels are submitted to IBAMA and are considered public records. Thus, the same sightings when submitted to SIMMAM must be set as “public”. As mentioned before, all the data held in the SIMMAM database, regardless of its public availability, can be seen by Brazilian environmental agencies (IBAMA and ICMBio).

Figure 6 Data in SIMMAM 3.0 on December 2023, separated bytype of record (sightings, strandings, accidental captures) and privacy status.

The option to allow government agencies to use the whole dataset is extremely important for management purposes, as it enables both environmental agencies to use even unpublished data generated by research institutions. But as the data is not available for the general public, it does not compromise their future use in academic publications. Also, the limited visualization of private data in the WebGIS (red dots in Figure 3), where details of the record such as species and date are not shown, serves as an indication for other researchers that a specific institution has data on marine mammals in a specific area, fostering collaborations among institutions.

In early 2024 ICMBio published an ordinance related to the national and regional stranding networks (ICMBio, 2024) and it states that data from stranded marine mammals collected by the institutions part of the networks should be stored in SIMMAM. This ordinance reinforces that SIMMAM is the national database for strandings and sightings and thus will be used to support actions taken for the conservation of aquatic mammals. Even though it has been the de facto database for the last two

decades, having a formal document defining it so, shows the commitment of the Brazilian government to support this initiative.

4. Conclusion

The amount of data presently held in SIMMAM shows its success as a repository for marine and freshwater mammals in Brazil. The use of open-source software since its first implementation was crucial to maintain it over its almost 20 years of existence. Even if some technologies previously used in it were discontinued, alternatives and solutions to replace them were always available. As there were no licence fees, SIMMAM could be maintained even in times when no financial support was available.

SIMMAM has also been cited in more than 70 academic works, including journal articles, thesis and dissertations. Its use is now widespread among the Brazilian scientific community, supporting different research initiatives. While there are other initiatives with wider scope such as OBIS and GBIF, as SIMMAM focus on a specific group (aquatic mammals) its use is simpler. Also, as its interface is in Portuguese, it is friendlier to undergraduate students from Brazil.

Due to its geographical coverage and extensive dataset, SIMMAM has been used as baseline data in many conservation projects. Faunal inventories using SIMMAM data has been used to support the creation of protected areas. Marine spatial planning, a strategic process for analysing and allocating marine areas to minimize conflicts between human activities, maximize benefits, and protect marine ecosystems (UNESCO-IOC 2021), relies heavily on occurrence data. Thus, we believe that SIMMAM will be invaluable to support such strategies in the future.

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